

EVALUATION OF THE SERUM LEVEL OF DEAMINATED GLIADIN PEPTIDE ANTIBODY (DGP) AMONG IRAQI CHILDREN WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS

Noor Haider Borhan Borhan

Department of Medical Microbiology, College of Medicine, University of Wasit, Wasit, Iraq

Muhammed Ali Al. Kabe

Head of department of physiology and medical physics, College of Medicine, University of Wasit, Wasit, Iraq

Krarr haidar Al-Anzi

University of Al-Qadisiyah

Abstract: Background: Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) and celiac disease (CD) are the most common autoimmune diseases in children and adolescents. These conditions often co-occur in the same patient, which may be due to both diseases sharing the same genetic background. This study aimed to assess the serum levels of deaminated gliadin peptide antibodies in diabetic pediatric populations in Wasit Province, Iraq.

Methods: This study recruited 100 T1DM patients and 60 healthy individuals, both sexes, under the age of 16 years. Five ml of blood was collected from each participant to determine the level of DGP-IgA and DGP-IgG using the ELISA technique. Fasting blood sugar (FBS), random blood sugar (RBS), and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1C) were also measured.

Results: The study found that there was a significant difference in the mean levels of DGP-IgA and DGP-IgG between patients and controls, with patients having a higher mean value of DGP-IgA than controls (14.58 ± 50.83 versus 1.82 ± 1.36). The same was shown in DGP-IgG, where the patients had a mean of 9.39 ± 42.18 compared to 1.87 ± 1.64 for controls.

Conclusion: The study reveals a significant difference in anti-DGP autoantibodies between T1DM patients when comparing them with healthy controls, putting them at high risk for developing CD.

Keywords: Celiac disease; deaminated gliadin peptide antibodies; type 1 diabetes mellitus.

1. Introduction

Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is an autoimmune disease characterized by beta cells destruction in the pancreas, leading to loss of insulin [1]. The prevalence of T1DM in the general population estimated at 5–10% of diabetes cases globally [2]. The clinical manifestations of T1DM begin to appear after the destruction of 80–90% of pancreatic β -cells, like polydipsia, polyphagia, polyuria, unexplained weight loss, and abdominal symptoms [3]. It can also cause acute and chronic complications, with acute complications

like diabetic coma, diabetic ketoacidosis and hypoglycemia, while chronic complications are either microvascular or macrovascular [4]. Type 1 diabetic patients have a higher risk to developing additional autoimmune disease, like celiac disease (CD) [5].

CD is an immune-mediated condition that occurs in genetically predisposed individuals when exposed to gluten, leading to atrophy in the small intestinal mucosa, which results in malabsorption syndrome. The clinical presentation of CD varies from the silent asymptomatic form to symptoms, which include gastrointestinal symptoms like abdominal pain, constipation, diarrhea, bloating, nausea, and vomiting, as well as non-gastrointestinal symptoms like short stature, anemia, neurological symptoms, delayed puberty, weight loss, osteoporosis or osteopenia, and dermatitis herpetiformis [6,7]. The prevalence of celiac disease in individuals with type 1 diabetes is approximately 6%, significantly higher than the 1% prevalence in the general population [6], because both of these conditions share an aberrant immunological response in the mucosa of the intestines, resulting in inflammation with a varying degrees of damage in the intestine tissue [7]. However, the actual reasons for the association between these conditions remain incompletely understood. A possible explanation is the fact that both conditions share the similar genetic background, namely HLA-DQ2 and/or DQ8, which are located on the short arm of chromosome 6, as well as the interaction between environmental and immunological factors [5].

Although the definitive diagnosis of CD relies on an intestinal biopsy, multiple serologic biomarkers are widely used for screening and monitoring dietary compliance in suspected cases [8], like the anti-DGP antibody (anti-DGP, IgA, and IgG types), which is one of the most common antibodies used for CD screening, especially in children [9]. It has been identified with sensitivity and specificity equivalent to IgA-tTG [10,11]. Certain studies found that anti-DGP, especially the IgG class, was positive in a majority of patients who tested negative for anti-tTG; this included children and people with selective IgA deficiency [12]. DGP are formed by selective gliadin deamination by the transglutaminase enzyme and glutamine substitution with glutamic acid, leading to the binding of gliadin fragments to HLA on antigen-presenting cells (APC), which is an important step in the immunological response to gluten that ultimately leads to CD [13,14].

Patients with CD prefer anti-DGP assays over anti-gliadin antibody because the DGP has a higher specificity for binding to circulating antibodies than native peptides [15]. In adults, DGP-IgA sensitivity ranges from 83.6% to 98.3%, with a specificity between 90.3% and 99.1%. While the sensitivity of DGP-IgG ranges from 84.4% to 96.7%, with a specificity of 98.5% to 100%, whereas in pediatric patients, the sensitivity of anti-DGP-IgA tests varies from 80.7% to 95.1%, with a specificity that falls between 86.3% and 93.1%, while the sensitivity of anti-DGP-IgG tests spans from 80.1% to 98.6%, with a specificity that falls between 86.0% and 96.9% [15,16]. This study aimed to evaluate the serum level of anti-DGP antibodies in T1DM children and adolescents in Wasit Province, Iraq.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study subject

A cross-sectional study was conducted from the 1st of September, 2023, to the 1st of January, 2024, at both Al-Shahid Fairooz General Hospital and Al-Karama Teaching Hospital, Wasit Province, Iraq. The study comprised a selection of 160 children and adolescents, aged under 16 years; both sexes were included, males and females. This population was divided into two groups, with 100 subjects who were already diagnosed with Type-1 diabetes mellitus and the remaining 60 as healthy controls who were free from CD signs and symptoms and had no history of any chronic disease.

The study involved carefully selected participants, ensuring the inclusion of only children within the designated age range. Exclusion criteria have been established through careful evaluation of the participants medical histories and self-reports to identify and exclude individuals with chronic or acute illnesses, genetic

disorders like Down syndrome, Turner syndrome, type 2 diabetes mellitus, mental retardation, autism, epilepsy, non-celiac gluten sensitivity, wheat and other food sensitivity, malignancies, and hemoglobinopathies, as well as those with acute and chronic infections.

2.2. Sample collection and processing

Blood samples were obtained from each participant through venipuncture. After that, blood samples were placed in a gel tube for serum separation. The blood was allowed to naturally coagulate for 30 minutes at room temperature, followed by centrifugation for 10 minutes at 1500 Xg (G-force) for serum separation. The separated serum was collected and divided into several sterile Eppendorf tubes, which were stored at -20 °C until use. Subsequently, each participant underwent two serologic tests: anti-deaminated gliadin peptide IgA and anti-deaminated gliadin peptide IgG antibody tests by the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) technique using commercially available kits of the Aeskulisa company (AESKULISA, Germany) with a cut-off value of >18 U/ml for each test. The results were analyzed according to the manufacturer's instructions on principle, procedure, and result interpretation.

2.3. Ethical Aspects

Prior to the enrolment in this study, written informed consent from all individuals or their parents or guardians was obtained, and the study protocol was followed by the Clinical Research Ethics and institutional guidelines set by the College of Medicine at the University of Wasit.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26 was used for data analysis. Data were expressed as mean± standard deviation values or median (interquartile range) for continuous numerical and as percentages and frequencies for categorical variables. Level of significance of ≤ 0.05 , considered as significant difference or association.

3. Results

3.1. Demographic characteristics

This study's results depend on the analysis of data collected from 160 samples (100 patients with diabetes and 60 healthy controls). Table 1 shows sociodemographic features in both study groups. It was found that males had the highest percentages in both groups; they represented 52% and 55% of both patients and controls, respectively. While females represented 48% of patients and 45% of controls, the highest percentage of the two groups was in the age groups from 11 to 15 years old, while those below 5 years old were representing the lowest percentages, and the age groups from 6 to 10 years old only represented 33% of patients and 38.3% of controls. The duration of disease among diabetic children was demonstrated in Figure 1. It shows that 50% of them were diagnosed with diabetes for 1-2 years, followed by 29% who had the disease for less than one year, and 21% of patients were diagnosed for 3-4 years.

Table 1: Socio-demographic features of the study groups (patients=100, controls=60).

Variables		Sample type		Total No. (%)	P-value
		No. (%)			
		Patients (n=100)	Controls (n=60)		
Sex	Male	52 (52%)	33 (55%)	85 (53.1%)	0.460
	Female	48 (48%)	27 (45%)	75 (46.9%)	
Age groups (years)	1-5	17 (17%)	13 (21.7%)	30 (18.8%)	0.713
	6-10	33 (33%)	23 (38.3%)	56 (35%)	
	11-15	50 (50%)	24 (40%)	74 (46.3%)	

Figure 1: Frequency distribution of diabetes mellitus duration among patient children (n=100).

3.2. Biochemical test

Table 2 shows a statistically significant difference in biochemical tests related to DM between the patient and control groups, with a P-value less than 0.001 for all the selected tests. Diabetic children showed higher levels of FBS, RBS, and HbA1C.

Table 2: Mean differences of the biochemical test among 160 children sample (patients=100, controls=60).

biochemical tests	Patients Mean \pm SD	Controls Mean \pm SD	P-value
FBS (mg/dl)	165.16 \pm 30.51	87.34 \pm 8.35	<0.001
RBS (mg/dl)	473.20 \pm 130.32	103.24 \pm 9.44	<0.001
HbA1C (%)	10.09 \pm 2.15	3.88 \pm 0.97	<0.001

SD= standard deviation, FBS= fasting blood sugar, RBS= random blood sugar, HbA1C= glycated haemoglobin.

3.3. Anti-deaminated gliadin peptide (DGP) antibodies

There is a significant difference in the mean levels of DGP-IgA and DGP-IgG between patients and controls, as seen in Table 3. Patients had a significantly higher mean level of DGP-IgA than controls (14.58 \pm 50.83 versus 1.82 \pm 1.36). The same was shown in DGP-IgG, where the patients had a mean of 9.39 \pm 42.18 compared to 1.87 \pm 1.64 for controls.

Table 3: Difference between patients and controls in autoantibodies (DGP-IgA and DGP-IgG) levels in the study sample (patients=100, controls=60).

Autoantibodies	Patients		Controls		P-value
	Mean (SD)	Median (IQR)	Mean (SD)	Median (IQR)	
DGP-IgA (U/ml)	14.58(50.83)	2.24(1.81)	1.82(1.36)	1.34(1.68)	0.001
DGP-IgG (U/ml)	9.39(42.18)	0.85(0.94)	1.87(1.64)	1.37(1.21)	0.001

SD = Standard deviation, IOQ= Interquartile range, DGP-IgA= anti-deaminated gliadin peptide immunoglobulin A, DGP-IgG= anti- deaminated gliadin peptide immunoglobulin G.

4. Discussion

T1DM is a significant predictor of celiac disease, which makes early screening beneficial for improving diabetic control, growth control, and avoiding extra-intestinal manifestations of the CD, such as osteopenia and malignancy [17]. It can also enhance the quality of life for diabetic patients by reducing the effects of CD on their health [18]. The present study documented that there are significant differences in the mean levels of DGP autoantibodies between T1DM patients and healthy controls (P value < 0.001), making these patients at high risk for CD development, which is in agreement with previous studies that suggested that DGP induces autoantibody production primarily to the entire development of histological lesions in the duodenum [19,20]. The present findings are also in line with other papers [21–23], which indicated that patients with CD may have anti-DGP antibodies even if they do not have anti-EMA and anti-tTG antibodies. In 2004, Schwertz et al., revealed that anti-DGP IgA tests have high sensitivity and demonstrated that anti-DGP IgA antibodies could be a useful test for CD diagnosis [24]. These results agree with the instructions of the North American Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition and the American College of Gastroenterology, which recommend anti-DGP antibody testing alongside with the anti-tTG IgA test to enhance the precision of CD diagnosis in children under 2 years old [25,26], as well as in adult patients [27,28], and reduce the need for measurement of total IgA in all individuals with suspected CD [23,29]. Other authors demonstrated that anti-DGP antibodies could be an effective method for early CD diagnosis, especially in young children [21,29]. So, it is recommended in the CD screening panel in diabetic patients alongside with anti-TG IgA [23]. By contrast, results differ in other studies [22,30,31], which discussed that anti-DGP tests are less precise than anti-tTG IgA tests and cannot be used as an alternative for anti-tTG tests when screening for CD-susceptible patients.

Conclusion

The study reveals a significant difference in anti-DGP autoantibodies between T1DM patients when comparing them with healthy controls, this suggests that these patients are at high risk for developing CD. Therefore, it is important to conduct routine CD screening tests for T1DM patients.

Acknowledgments

We express thanks to all the study participants and their families for their participation in this research, and we extend our sincere thanks to the staff of AI-Shahid Fairouz General Hospital and AI-Karama Teaching Hospital for their collaboration in this study.

Funding statement: This study did not get any funding.

List of abbreviations: CD: celiac disease; T1DM: type 1 diabetes mellitus; HLA-DQ: human leukocyte antigen-DQ; anti-tTG Ab: anti-tissue transglutaminase antibody; APCs: antigen presenting cells; anti-DGP Ab= anti-deaminated gliadin antibody; FBS: fasting blood sugar; RBS: random blood sugar; HbA1C: glycated hemoglobin; ELISA= enzyme linked immunosorbent assay.

References

1. L. A. DiMeglio, C. Evans-Molina, and R. A. Oram, “Type 1 diabetes,” *Lancet*, vol. 391, no. 10138, pp. 2449–2462, 2018.
2. G. D. Ogle *et al.*, “Global estimates of incidence of type 1 diabetes in children and adolescents: Results from the International Diabetes Federation Atlas,” *Diabetes Res. Clin. Pract.*, vol. 183, p. 109083, 2022.
3. D. Care, “Care in diabetes—2022,” *Diabetes Care*, vol. 45, p. S17, 2022.

4. A. Rewers, "Acute metabolic complications in diabetes," 2021.
5. S. Husby *et al.*, "European Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition guidelines for the diagnosis of celiac disease," *J. Pediatr. Gastroenterol. Nutr.*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 136–160, 2012.
6. R. Al Kindi, A. Al Salmani, R. Al Hadhrami, and M. Al Maashani, "Epidemiology of Celiac Disease," in *Celiac Disease and Gluten-Free Diet*, IntechOpen, 2023.
7. S. K. Bhadada, A. Rastogi, A. Agarwal, R. Kochhar, R. Kochhar, and A. Bhansali, "Comparative study of clinical features of patients with celiac disease & those with concurrent celiac disease & type 1 diabetes mellitus," *Indian J. Med. Res.*, vol. 145, no. 3, pp. 334–338, 2017.
8. A. Maheshwari, Z. He, M. N. Weidner, P. Lin, R. Bober, and F. J. Del Rosario, "Influence of age and type 1 diabetes mellitus on serological test for celiac disease in children," *Pediatr. Gastroenterol. Hepatol. Nutr.*, vol. 24, no. 2, p. 218, 2021.
9. O. Olen *et al.*, "Antibodies against deamidated gliadin peptides and tissue transglutaminase for diagnosis of pediatric celiac disease," *J. Pediatr. Gastroenterol. Nutr.*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 695–700, 2012.
10. G. N. Catassi, A. Pulvirenti, C. Monachesi, C. Catassi, and E. Lionetti, "Diagnostic accuracy of IgA anti-transglutaminase and IgG anti-deamidated gliadin for diagnosis of celiac disease in children under two years of age: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *Nutrients*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 7, 2021.
11. I. Brusca *et al.*, "The old and new tests for celiac disease: which is the best test combination to diagnose celiac disease in pediatric patients?," *Clin. Chem. Lab. Med.*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 111–117, 2012.
12. A. Al-Toma *et al.*, "European Society for the Study of Coeliac Disease (ESsCD) guideline for coeliac disease and other gluten-related disorders," *United Eur. Gastroenterol. J.*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 583–613, 2019.
13. I. Brusca, "Overview of biomarkers for diagnosis and monitoring of celiac disease," *Adv. Clin. Chem.*, vol. 68, pp. 1–55, 2015.
14. S.-W. Qiao, L. M. Sollid, and R. S. Blumberg, "Antigen presentation in celiac disease," *Curr. Opin. Immunol.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 111–117, 2009.
15. S. N. Y. Alkemawy and S. N. H. Alsaltani, "Hospital in Baghdad," *Prof.(Dr) RK Sharma*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 904, 2021.
16. J. Calado and M. Verdelho Machado, "Celiac disease revisited," *GE-Portuguese J. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 111–124, 2022.
17. M. Freemark and L. L. Levitsky, "Screening for celiac disease in children with type 1 diabetes: two views of the controversy," *Diabetes Care*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 1932–1939, 2003.
18. E. M. Albatayneh, N. A. Alnawaiseh, S. A. Al-Sarayreh, Y. M. Al-sarairah, E. M. Al-Zayadneh, and M. A. Abu-lobbad, "Serologic screening of celiac disease in patients with Type 1 diabetes," *J. Endocrinol. Metab.*, vol. 8, no. 2–3, pp. 37–42, 2018.
19. D. Basso *et al.*, "New screening tests enrich anti-transglutaminase results and support a highly sensitive two-test based strategy for celiac disease diagnosis," *Clin. Chim. acta*, vol. 412, no. 17–18, pp. 1662–1667, 2011.
20. K. Kurppa *et al.*, "Antibodies against deamidated gliadin peptides in early-stage celiac disease," *J. Clin. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 673–678, 2011.
21. C. Dahle, A. Hagman, S. Ignatova, and M. Ström, "Antibodies against deamidated gliadin peptides

- identify adult coeliac disease patients negative for antibodies against endomysium and tissue transglutaminase,” *Aliment. Pharmacol. Ther.*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 254–260, 2010.
22. A. Shatnawei, A. H. AlNababteh, R. D. Govender, S. Al-Shamsi, A. AlJarrah, and R. H. Al-Rifai, “Mode of presentation and performance of serology assays for diagnosing celiac disease: A single-center study in the United Arab Emirates,” *Front. Nutr.*, vol. 10, p. 1107017, 2023.
 23. S. Rashtak, M. W. Ettore, H. A. Homburger, and J. A. Murray, “Comparative usefulness of deamidated gliadin antibodies in the diagnosis of celiac disease,” *Clin. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 426–432, 2008.
 24. E. Schwertz *et al.*, “Serologic assay based on gliadin-related nonapeptides as a highly sensitive and specific diagnostic aid in celiac disease,” *Clin. Chem.*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 2370–2375, 2004.
 25. I. D. Hill *et al.*, “NASPGHAN clinical report on the diagnosis and treatment of gluten-related disorders,” *J. Pediatr. Gastroenterol. Nutr.*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 156–165, 2016.
 26. A. Rubio-Tapia, I. D. Hill, C. P. Kelly, A. H. Calderwood, and J. A. Murray, “ACG clinical guidelines: diagnosis and management of celiac disease,” *Off. J. Am. Coll. Gastroenterol. ACG*, vol. 108, no. 5, pp. 656–676, 2013.
 27. N. A. Hoerter *et al.*, “Diagnostic yield of isolated deamidated gliadin peptide antibody elevation for celiac disease,” *Dig. Dis. Sci.*, vol. 62, pp. 1272–1276, 2017.
 28. M. J. Gould, H. Brill, M. A. Marcon, N. J. Munn, and C. M. Walsh, “In screening for celiac disease, deamidated gliadin rarely predicts disease when tissue transglutaminase is normal,” *J. Pediatr. Gastroenterol. Nutr.*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 20–25, 2019.
 29. K. Lewandowska *et al.*, “Celiac antibodies in children with type 1 diabetes—a diagnostic validation study,” *Autoimmunity*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 81–88, 2018.
 30. D. Basso *et al.*, “Antibodies against synthetic deamidated gliadin peptides for celiac disease diagnosis and follow-up in children,” *Clin. Chem.*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 150–157, 2009.
 31. A. C. Schyum and J. J. Rumessen, “Serological testing for celiac disease in adults,” *United Eur. Gastroenterol. J.*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 319–325, 2013.